

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report #2 for **TEBT-** **2025-0020**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Reporting Quality of Systematic Review Protocols in Environmental and Occupational Toxicology: A meta-epidemiology study
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0020
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785
Editor Declaration of Interests	This manuscript is an official publication of the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC). The Handling Editor is Editor-in-Chief of EBT and also a contractor for EBTC where, in both roles, they are responsible for ensuring that EBTC publications comply with the standards and goals of the Collaboration. The Handling Editor was also responsible for the policies on systematic reviews at Environment International, which feature prominently in the manuscript. These are viewed as managed interests, where publisher and EBTC policies to minimise the risk of these interests compromising the handling of the manuscript have been followed.
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Recommendation	Revise

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

This manuscript analyses the reporting quality of systematic review protocols that are concerned with the health effects of chemical exposures.

The data collection and analysis methods follow the plan described in the accepted protocol ([Pavlovic et al. 2025](#)) and the authors have provided a discussion that is concordant with the data they have collected.

The comments from the handling editor and reviewers mainly focus on further developing the discussion of the results of the study, as there is a lot more that could be said that would also be justified.

Seriousness of issues identified with write-up of study	The issues are not limitations as such, more an opportunity to further develop the work that has been done.
Potential additional work to overcome issues	Some additional data collection and analysis, and some further discussion with reference to related literature have been recommended. This could take 3-4 days, in my estimation.
Acceptability of characterising limitations instead of additional data collection and analysis	If the authors did not have capacity to do this extra work then the manuscript is already effectively publishable, but it would be a lost opportunity not to do it.

Reviewers' Comments

Note about reviewer comments: Reviewer comments have been aggregated into the structured feedback below by the handling editor. Comments may have been edited for constructiveness or continuity, or annotated to indicate how the authors may consider responding. Comments are numbered for ease of reference.

1. Overall impressions of the manuscript

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 2

1. This manuscript is well-written, and the methods appropriate for the stated purpose.
2. I would appreciate more detail on the key findings highlighted in the abstract. These findings are described with minimal supporting details in the text.
3. This manuscript reports an assessment of the quality of systematic review protocols in the fields of environmental and occupational toxicology. The manuscript is well-written and provides insightful details into environmental / occupational toxicological protocols. I have highlighted a few areas in which further context and/or detail would be helpful, especially for areas that are highlighted in the abstract but are only minimally referenced in the text.

Reviewer 3

4. Authors are presenting an overview of the reporting quality of systematic review protocols in environmental and occupational toxicology research. The manuscript is concise, clear, and cohesive.

We sincerely thank the reviewers for their thoughtful and constructive comments, which have helped improve the quality and clarity of our manuscript and have also identified valuable directions for future research.

2. Are the introduction, rationale, and hypotheses the same as in the accepted protocol?

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 1

5. Yes, the authors adhered to their planned methods. Where they deviated slightly, they described thoroughly in the Deviations from the Protocol section (2.5).

3. Were the collected data able to test the stated hypotheses by satisfying the approved outcome-neutral conditions?

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 3

6. Adherence to the PRISMA-P checklist is a simple yet effective approach for assessing reporting quality.

7. Why were protocols on PROSPERO and similar platforms not eligible? The preceding protocol for this work suggests that reasons may include difficulties in searching PROSPERO or a lack of peer-review of protocols published to online platforms. Elaboration and justification regarding this inclusion criterion are lacking.

Thank you for your comment. Obviously, this aspect was sufficiently clear during the protocol review. Therefore, we would refrain from modifying the manuscript. To elaborate a bit further, we excluded non-peer-reviewed protocols as this would have introduced too many confounding factors that would require more intensive stratification of the data and analysis. In addition, PROSPERO is focussed on direct human health outcomes, which may have led to an underrepresentation of protocols on environmental and occupational toxicology questions. In addition, as a potentially large amount of relevant human observational studies could have exceeded the available capacity for voluntary work, conducting a smaller-scale project well was preferred.

4. Are the additional post-hoc or exploratory analyses (if any) added by the authors justified, methodologically sound, and informative?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

There were no additional unplanned analyses. There is some additional data collection and light analysis suggested by the reviewers in the next section of this report - the authors should be careful to make it clear that this is additional to the original protocol (which I am sure they will do).

5. Are the authors' findings, based on the planned and unplanned analyses, justified?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

The reviewers largely agree that what is discussed is justified. What the reviewers are asking for is more development of the implications of the findings, as there is a lot more that could be said that would also be justified. As there are lots of comments to respond to, the authors may wish to develop a list of discussion points based on the reviewers' suggestions and use this to structure their response to reviewer comments (and the development of the discussion section in the manuscript).

Some of the comments may require some additional data collection, but most of it does not look too onerous and could significantly improve the manuscript.

Just reflecting on this, I wonder if the two primary issues raised by the reviewer comments might be:

(a) If the authors could find out if peer-review makes a protocol better-reported? It may not: if the journal review process is not sufficiently rigorous then journal-published protocols may not be much better than PROSPERO registrations, but they should be a bit better. This would be important, as it would suggest peer-review makes a difference, just not a big difference (or possibly, big enough difference if preregistration is supposed to more-or-less guarantee a very rigorous final review). I wouldn't ask the authors to do any additional data collection and analysis, but if they could find studies of the quality of PROSPERO registrations, that should at least provide a point of comparison.

We thank the reviewer for this valuable suggestion and agree that this is an important question worthy of investigation. However, we believe it should be addressed as a distinct research objective with its own dedicated methodology and pre-specified protocol, rather than being incorporated as an additional *post hoc* analysis in the present study. Conducting such an analysis would require separate planning and resources to ensure it is performed rigorously and appropriately.

(b) Since there are several Environment International protocols included in the authors' study, and we know EI is particularly exacting when it comes to SR standards, could these be looked at as a subgroup in a secondary analysis, and see if there is a suggestive difference? This would just be an additional secondary analysis to support discussion and hypothesising.

Thank you for your comment. We considered conducting subgroup analyses but ultimately decided against them because (a) doing so would deviate from the pre-specified protocol, (b) the sample size is too limited to support meaningful or generalizable conclusions across journals, and (c) it would be difficult to justify treating individual journals differently, while applying such analyses uniformly across all journals would be excessive and not informative.

Reviewer comments

Editor (from triage, prior to peer-review)

8. The discussion is well-written but could perhaps be further developed, especially around the knowledge gaps left by the study - what it is we don't know in relation to the quality of systematic review protocols in toxicology, and how future research could address these. I think this is important because the authors have investigated a very indirect measure of the quality of a SRP. While they did this for good reason, it does put quite tight constraints on what can be learned from this study and makes it harder to connect to broader concerns about the quality of research (we know that SRPs are reported reasonably well, but what that tells us seems quite limited).

We thank the reviewer for this insightful comment and agree that our assessment captures an indirect measure of systematic review protocol quality, namely the completeness of reporting rather than methodological quality itself. We also agree that it is important to discuss the remaining knowledge gaps and the implications of our findings in this context. In response, we have expanded the Discussion by adding a dedicated section on future perspectives, highlighting what remains unknown about the quality of systematic review protocols in toxicology and outlining research directions to assess methodological quality more directly and to better understand how protocol quality influences the conduct and reliability of systematic reviews.

9. Just thinking about this, obviously SRPs are still quite rare (if there was some valid way of estimating how many journal-published SRs there are compared to journal-published SRPs, that might be helpful), and we know how well reported they are but not how valid the planned methods are. We also don't know about the impact of the journal-published SRP on the final quality of SRs - and it is quality we should ultimately be interested in (this is the difference with the Menon paper - there, we looked at a closer proxy for rigour

than reporting quality, and as follow-up work this paper looked at something easier to study but is a bit less revealing about SRP quality).

This is a valid comment; as such, we have acknowledged this limitation in the Discussion section and highlighted it as an area for future research. In the Limitations section, we added: “Finally, this assessment is relevant at the protocol level but provides limited information on quality at the final publication level; a well-reported protocol does not equate to a rigorous or well-reported SR. Further studies on this topic are warranted, as mentioned in the section above.” In the final paragraph of the Discussion, we added: “This work provides a foundation for future research and highlights several important avenues for further investigation. Future studies should assess the impact of protocol development and preregistration on the methodological rigor of SRs in environmental health, for example by comparing the methodological quality of reviews with registered or published protocols to those conducted without a protocol. Additionally, comparing the quality of protocols published in registries with those published in peer-reviewed journals would help determine the added value of peer review in improving protocol quality.”

10. Some discussion of these issues, and the sort of research that should be done to address them, so that this EBTC publication gives a clear steer to the rest of the field, would be welcome, I think. (This should not be perfunctory, the authors should consider in some detail what ought to be done next.)

We thank the reviewer for this thoughtful suggestion and agree that it is important to provide clear guidance on future research priorities for the field. In response, we have expanded the Discussion by adding a dedicated paragraph on future directions that goes beyond a brief acknowledgment of remaining gaps: “*Although the overall reporting quality of SRPs assessed in this study could be considered good, follow-up studies investigating the appropriateness of how items were addressed and the adherence of SRs to published SRPs are needed; such protocols-papers comparisons have been performed in other fields, for systematic reviews with PROSPERO protocols and published protocols (Hopewell et al., 2002; Hu et al., 2021; Koensgen et al., 2019; Siebert et al., 2023). Importantly, reporting completeness should not be equated with methodological rigor (Faggion Jr, 2023). A protocol may comprehensively report suboptimal or inappropriate methods, while a methodologically robust protocol may nevertheless omit important reporting details (Faggion Jr, 2023; K. Pussegoda et al., 2017).*

Accordingly, our findings should be interpreted as an assessment of transparency rather than methodological validity.”

11. In addition to the 2016 publication where we introduced our plans for SRs at Environment International, [in 2022 Nicolas Roth and I reflected on how well our plans were working and what we had learned](#). This might be of interest to the authors, and may be a relevant citation for para 1 of the Discussion (though do not take this as instruction to include it!). This may also give the authors some ideas about how to discuss the issues of whether and how the quality of SRPs might impact the quality of SRs, and how this could be investigated.

*We thank the reviewer for this helpful suggestion and for drawing our attention to this publication. We agree that the experience of *Environment International* in promoting methodological rigor in systematic reviews is highly relevant, particularly given that it was the journal with the greatest representation in our sample. We have considered these insights in revising the Discussion and agree that understanding whether and how the quality of systematic review protocols influences the quality of completed systematic reviews is an important avenue for future research. However, we believe that addressing this question rigorously would require a dedicated study with a pre-specified methodology and protocol, rather than a *post hoc* analysis within the scope of the present work.*

Reviewer 1

12. I appreciated the clarity of the discussion section, and I believe that it did an excellent job of not overstating or overgeneralizing findings. I particularly liked the paragraph on funding (beginning line 377), because it tied in the findings from this research with findings from other research and also provided a message about what could be done/why it is important. I would suggest that the authors consider strengthening their discussion section with additional reflection and comparison to other research to see where findings diverged, where they were similar to other work, and what lessons can be drawn from the new additions from this research. [I have highlighted] a few areas that I thought could potentially benefit from additional discussion.

Thank you for the comment, but we do not see highlighted text.

13. I am very interested in the authors' thoughts on whether full protocols should always be published as journal articles, or whether study registration (with fields like those in

PROSPERO, which aligns with PRISMA-P) meets the goals of a protocol. Should more people be encouraged to publish full protocols as journal articles? Why? Is there any research on protocols that are journal articles vs. registrations that you could comment on? Will people who go through the effort of publishing a full protocol be more likely to adhere to their protocol and/or report their findings better later, for example? I believe literature exists on comparing protocols for RCTs in various sources, for example, that may provide some insight. I am curious about this primarily because we don't often recommend publishing a full protocol, but perhaps we should. [Editor: I expect there is research on e.g. completeness of PRISMA registrations, and I also expect that completeness of PRISMA registrations is inconsistent. Peer-review should, in theory, improve the completeness of a protocol - but it might not improve them by much, so the implications of that for journal policy could be developed. For example, at EBT and Environment International, compliance with standards is the responsibility of the editor, it is not left entirely to peer-reviewers because of the uneven results of doing this. Environment International just [updated a previous editorial](#) that may touch on this issue. Discussion within the limits of what the authors have found would be welcome.]

Thank you for your comment. We cannot draw conclusions about whether the peer-review process inherently improves reporting quality in toxicology SRPs compared with non-peer-reviewed repositories, as protocols from such repositories were excluded based on our eligibility criteria.

That said, there are several practical advantages associated with peer-reviewed protocol publications. First, once published in a journal, they are generally more discoverable and less likely to be modified or replaced over time, providing a stable and citable record. Second, although peer review does not guarantee methodological rigor, it does serve as an additional level of scrutiny that is absent for protocols posted in non-peer-reviewed repositories. Consequently, protocols with methodological limitations may proceed to a systematic review without external evaluation.

14. **Though** this research focuses on reporting quality, and not methodological quality, the discussion section could be used to further discuss existing evidence of how reporting quality can impact or suggest shortcomings with methodological quality. There are several studies that look at reporting (usually PRISMA) and also use AMSTAR, for example, that may be good to discuss.

Thank you for your comment. We included in our Discussion section emphasis that this study is assessing reporting and not methodological quality: *Importantly, reporting completeness should not be equated with methodological rigor (Faggion Jr, 2023). A protocol may comprehensively report suboptimal or inappropriate methods, while a methodologically robust protocol may nevertheless omit important reporting details (Faggion Jr, 2023; K. Pussegoda et al., 2017). Accordingly, our findings should be interpreted as an assessment of transparency rather than methodological validity.*

In addition, this was previously requested to be delineating during protocol development (Whaley, P. (2024). Evaluation Reports for TEBT-2024-0002 | Pavlovic et al. Zenodo.). Comparing the results of our study with those studies that have completely different aim of assessing methodological quality would might expand discussion in different direction. Thus, we would avoid referring to studies performing methodological quality assessments, at this stage of our study.

15. **Are there** any comparisons with literature that looks at other types of protocol (e.g., SPIRIT) that would be useful?

- Yes, comparison using SPIRIT recommendations have been conducted. We added the following references to the discussion:

Gryaznov D, von Niederhäusern B, Speich B, et al Reporting quality of clinical trial protocols: a repeated cross-sectional study about the Adherence to SPIrit

Recommendations in Switzerland, CA Canada and GERMANY (ASPIRE-SCAGE) BMJ Open 2022;12:e053417. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2021-053417

- Speich, B., Odutayo, A., Peckham, N. et al. A longitudinal assessment of trial protocols approved by research ethics committees: The Adherence to SPIrit REcommendations in the UK (ASPI

And we have added the following text to the discussion: *"Consistent with our findings, the ASPIRE-SCAGE and ASPIRE-UK studies reported modest improvements in adherence to SPIRIT recommendations over time, although reporting remained incomplete overall and important gaps persisted, particularly in investigator- or non-industry-sponsored trial protocols."*

16. Are there journals that are more successful in implementing protocol publication than others?

That is an interesting question, considering that acceptance of systematic review protocols for publication remains quite limited. This is an assumption from experience rather than a reflection

of our dataset, but journals dedicated to systematic reviews and/or that have a strong open science policy probably have a higher number of published protocols than journals that do not (and may already not always accept reviews self).

17. Paragraph lines 372-376: I believe there is significantly more literature on this topic (including checklist but not being compliant with it) out there, and perhaps specifically on SPIRIT or other protocol reporting guidelines that could be interesting to discuss in more depth.

Thank you for mentioning this. Please refer yourself to our answer to comment 15.

18. It may be helpful to further speculate on specific research that should be done to follow up on this work. What research do you think would be key next steps for the toxicology community to take on? Why? What will they add to the literature? I realize there is one sentence in the conclusions, but you may wish to add more information in the Discussion that directly leads to these future lines of work. [Editor: This seems a good suggestion - the original concept for this EBTC research was somewhat broader and more focused on understanding the quality of SR protocols and the relationship with the quality of final SRs, though of course plans changed, and during my triage checks I thought more could be done in the discussion to interpret the findings.]

Thank you for your comment. One of the directions of future work will compare the quality of the non- and peer-reviewed protocols.

This direction is mentioned at the end of Discussion section: *“Although the overall reporting quality of SRPs assessed in this study could be considered good, follow-up studies investigating the appropriateness of how items were addressed and the adherence of SRs to published SRPs are needed; such protocols-papers comparisons have been performed in other fields, for systematic reviews with PROSPERO protocols and published protocols...”*

Reviewer 2

19. In general, the authors should verify that conclusions are well-supported by the reported results. I've added some specifics below where the authors might reassess if there might be additional information to support the observations/conclusions.

We acknowledge the reviewer's comment.

20. Line 163: Why 4 reviewers?

We had 4 volunteers who were interested in contributing, and the workload has been divided in pairs.

This also allowed the work to be done more quickly than by only 2 persons.

21. Line 243: Is exclusion of >98% records typical? Can you provide context on whether this is high or typical?

We agree with the reviewer that the number of records identified is high. However, such yields are not unusual when using a highly sensitive literature search strategy, particularly for methodological reviews where maximizing recall is prioritized over specificity. We also agree that a systematic comparison with other systematic reviews and meta-epidemiological studies in environmental health and toxicology would be informative. Unfortunately, conducting such an analysis would require substantial additional work and falls beyond the scope and available resources of the present study.

More broadly, we appreciate this and the other thoughtful suggestions provided by the reviewers. While not all could be incorporated within the scope of the current work, they highlight valuable directions for future research. We believe that our study was conducted rigorously, including the use of a pre-published, peer-reviewed protocol to prespecify the methodology and analysis.

22. Line 258/Figure 2. It's interesting that the number of published protocols in these fields has declined since 2021. This finding is mentioned in the abstract but not the discussion. I think this warrants being addressed in the discussion. In the authors' opinion, what might be possible underlying reasons for this trend?

We noticed the trend but were not inclined to make any conclusions considering the sample size of included protocols that is rather small.

23. Lines 283-291: Can you provide more explicit details on how the reader should interpret these findings? The SRP is quite broad, so its hard to draw any insights from the list of outcomes presented here. Please add details to help the reader interpret this information on studied outcomes. What knowledge can be drawn from this analysis?

Thank you for your comment. We consider outcome categorization to be an important addition, as meta-research is typically concentrated in areas with enough primary studies and where there are substantial or emerging public health concerns.

This approach also allows for a broader interpretive perspective. In the discussion, we aimed to highlight how the distribution of evidence across organ systems may indirectly

reflect shifting priorities in environmental and occupational health research, which are often influenced by patterns of funding, policy attention, and societal concern over time.

24. Table 3: Why are the types not always listed in logical (descending) order? For example, the types of “Outcomes per Organ System” are not listed in descending order.

Thank you for noticing this; we have corrected Table 3 accordingly to ensure all categories are shown in descending order.

25. Lines 303-304: Please say more regarding how often the role of funder/sponsor was reported, especially since this finding is referenced in the abstract

We referred in our results the number of times the role of the funder/sponsor was reported: “...In all 37 assessed protocols, authors reported the funder/sponsor, but in only 30% (11 / 37) of cases, had they reported the role of the funder/sponsor.” And in Discussion: “Of all administrative items assessed, role of funder was the most under-reported (30% (11 / 37).”

26. Lines 369-371: I do not see any reference in the results that analyze protocols by journal. This could be interesting and I would like to hear more. I suggest adding this analysis to the results, or not discussing it as part of the discussion section.

We did initially consider incorporating this analysis. However, given the relatively small sample size, we were concerned that stratification by journal and further correlating with impact factor could lead to unstable estimates and risk overinterpretation of patterns that may be driven by chance rather than true underlying differences. In addition, we felt it was important to avoid drawing overly generalized or potentially misleading conclusions from limited data, particularly in a context where journal-level comparisons could easily be misconstrued as evaluative judgments of publication quality.

For these reasons, we chose not to include this analysis in the current manuscript. We have also moderated the discussion accordingly to avoid implying interpretations that are not directly supported by the available data. We appreciate the reviewer’s suggestion and agree that this would be a valuable direction for future research in a larger, more adequately powered dataset.

Reviewer 3

27. **It would have** been interesting to gain an understanding of the proportion of SR protocols relative to published SR in the field (or a relevant subfield), rather than merely the

absolute number of protocols. Authors may consider adding estimates to their discussion section, to help readers contextualize findings.

Thank you for this insightful suggestion. A previous study by Tsujimoto et al. (2017) examined the publication status of systematic review protocols registered in PROSPERO during its first year of operation (2012–2013), although not specifically in the field of environmental health. They reported that approximately 26% of the sampled protocols had not resulted in a published systematic review at the time of assessment, or at least no corresponding publication could be identified. Conducting a comparable analysis in environmental health would be challenging within the scope of the present study, as it would require comprehensive tracking and matching of protocols to subsequent publications. Nevertheless, we agree that evaluating the proportion of registered protocols that ultimately lead to published systematic reviews would be valuable and have identified this as a potential direction for future research.

Tsujimoto H, Tsujimoto Y, Kataoka Y. Unpublished systematic reviews and financial support: a meta-epidemiological study. *BMC Res Notes*. 2017 Dec 6;10(1):703. doi: 10.1186/s13104-017-3043-5.

28. Also, the implications of not including grey literature like PROSPERO protocols should be addressed in the limitations section, as this and similar platforms are extremely popular for registering protocols, by explicitly discussing the potential effects on the current overview findings (e.g., regarding selection bias), rather than simply stating that grey literature was not included.

Thank you for your comment. Obviously, this aspect was sufficiently clear during the protocol review. Therefore, we would refrain from modifying the manuscript. To elaborate a bit further, we excluded non-peer-reviewed protocols as this would have introduced too many confounding factors that would require more intensive stratification of the data and analysis. In addition, PROSPERO is focussed on direct human health outcomes, which may have led to an underrepresentation of protocols on environmental and occupational toxicology questions. In addition, as a potentially large amount of relevant human observational studies could have exceeded the available capacity for voluntary work, conducting a smaller-scale project well was preferred.

29. The discussion paragraph on the importance of disclosing funder roles is important. Authors may elaborate in the discussion section on why reporting quality matters for systematic review protocols in toxicology research- what is the current context of evidence syntheses in the toxicology research field, and what can be recommended? Some questions for sparking ideas:

- a. Why are protocols so important especially right now, relative to current systematic review practices and developments (e.g., large-scale and cross-disciplinary consortia, automation and AI in evidence synthesis, etc...)
- b. What specific aspects of systematic reviews of occupational and environmental toxicology research make pre-specified protocols with high reporting quality so important? For instance, it may be especially important to pre-specify risk of bias assessment methods for systematic reviews of observational studies. For example, specifying lists of confounders/ co-exposures/ covariates of interest, acceptable exposure assessment methods, and other quality indicators may require greater review team involvement, planning, detailed documentation, etc. compared to assessing analogous study processes in experimental studies (e.g., randomization), to ensure both i) appropriate methods and ii) correct implementation by the review team- all facilitated via comprehensive protocols. Further, methodological approaches may arguably have especially impactful implications for systematic reviews of observational studies- making comprehensive protocols all the more important.

Thank you for this extremely important and valuable suggestion. We have expanded the discussion to better contextualize the importance of high-quality protocol reporting in systematic reviews within environmental and occupational toxicology.

We now emphasize that, in this field, evidence synthesis often relies heavily on complex observational data, heterogeneous exposure assessments, and variable confounding structures, which require extensive pre-specification of methodological decisions (e.g., confounders, co-exposures, exposure metrics, and risk of bias approaches). In the absence of such pre-specification, there is a higher risk of inconsistent or post hoc decision-making that may influence review conclusions.

We also highlight that this is particularly relevant in the current landscape of evidence synthesis, where reviews are increasingly conducted within large consortia and supported by emerging automated and AI-assisted tools. In this context, detailed and transparent protocols are essential to ensure methodological consistency, reproducibility, and accountability across review teams.

Regarding the importance of protocols, systematic review protocols are valuable across all research fields but are particularly relevant in toxicology and environmental health, where review findings may directly inform regulatory guidance and public health policies. Ensuring that these protocols are rigorous and transparently reported is therefore essential to support the credibility, reproducibility, and trustworthiness of the resulting systematic reviews and the decisions based on them.

Finally, we have linked this to the importance of clearly reporting funder involvement, as part of broader transparency practices that support trust in evidence synthesis in policy-relevant areas such as toxicology and environmental health. We thank the reviewer for this valuable recommendation, which has strengthened the framing of our discussion.

6. Other comments

Reviewer comments

Editor (from triage, prior to peer-review)

30. In Appendix B3 (Included protocols) I noticed that “Environment International” is misspelled once as “Environmental International”, creating a count of 10 rather than 11 occurrences for the journal in the dataset. This does not appear to have affected the results, but the authors should check to make sure no coding errors have occurred that affect the counts in their data (it will affect the reusability of their data).

Thank you for pointing this out. We updated the Supplementary Material, Appendix B3.

Reviewer 1

31. I wasn't sure how lines 356-361 followed the prior paragraph. It seems like it could be its own paragraph, perhaps with expanded detail.

Thank you for this comment. We separated it into different paragraphs, but this should be used as an interpretation why certain systems were more commonly the outcomes of interest in systematic review protocols, compared to others.

32. Do you have any thoughts on why NAMs were included so rarely?

We have several considerations that may help explain this pattern. First, our definition of adverse effects was primarily focused on human health outcomes, which may have favored the inclusion of epidemiological studies. Second, much of the meta-research in this area is conducted by researchers with public health backgrounds, who may be less familiar with new approach methodologies. Moreover, less RoB tools are currently available for NAMs studies in systematic reviews, making their quality appraisal more challenging.

33. For the paragraph beginning on line 395, I think it would be helpful to say 'Data management procedures **(Q6)** ... 'Data extraction **(Q8)**' procedure... and then "This could be partially explained by our assessment approach, where **these** two items..."

Thank you for this comment. We incorporated your suggestion.

34. The authors note that they found SRPs where the confidence in the body of evidence was not addressed, and specifically that there may be "unawareness of toxicology-specific risk of bias and evidence integration tools", but there is no mention of what those tools are. Could something be added to highlight which tools are toxicology-specific?

[Editor: [This EBTC paper](#) may be helpful for this, although I note I am one of the authors and am not requiring the authors to cite it, just alerting them to it as a resource.]

Thank you for your comment. We expanded our discussion, indicating what Confidence in cumulative evidence is, what are the most common approaches in toxicology used for assessment of it, why it is important, why it could be omitted and what are the consequences of omission.

35. Could you note the domain that Frost's article was in as part of the paragraph beginning on line 406? It might help to give slightly more context for that. I specifically noted that Frost's article title says protocols were inadequate, but you didn't really comment on how your findings differ substantially, e.g., so that may be helpful to add as well.

The role of funder/sponsor information, confidence in cumulative evidence, and risk of bias were also the items poorly reported for published protocols in the study by Frost et al., showing concordance with our results and a pattern present across disciplines, at least in the domain of peer-reviewed literature (Frost et al., 2022).

36. I appreciate the authors' commitment to clear reporting, and I deeply appreciate the authors' attention to detail in reporting the search. There are two items where additional information is required for complete reporting, however: item 1 (database names) and

item 2 (multi-database searching).

- a. Item 1: Please state which platform was used to search Embase. If it was Embase via Embase.com, it is sufficient to say Embase.com instead of Embase, though ideally, please note if you were also searching in Embase Classic and/or Preprints; if it was Embase via Ovid, please make sure to report the full database name (e.g., Embase, Preprint, Clinical Trials and Embase Classic* 1947 – Present, updated daily). If you are using Embase.com and are not sure whether your institution has access to Embase Classic and/or Preprints as part of your subscription, and/or whether they are automatically searched by default, you can check by going to the Advanced search and then Sources. If you have Embase Classic available, it will be listed as a source. I presume that you searched PubMed via PubMed.gov and not via a 3 party tool like EndNote, but if you searched it a different way, please indicate that. Scopus is only searchable via Scopus.com and its API; if you used the API, though I don't believe you did, please indicate that.

Thank you for your comment, we used [Embase.com](https://www.embase.com), [Pubmed.gov](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/), [Scopus.com](https://www.scopus.com). We did not use Scopus API.

- b. Item 2: Web of Science is a platform, not a database, so you did search multiple databases simultaneously (each institution has unique subscriptions and default search settings for this tool, so it is critical to list the databases individually). The easiest way to do this is if you have an export of the search strategy that you saved when you ran the search, as it lists the institution's entitlements for that search and whether you only searched within specific databases. For example:

Entitlements:

- WOS.IC: 1993 to 2026
- WOS.CCR: 1985 to 2026
- WOS.SCI: 1900 to 2026
- WOS.AHCI: 1975 to 2026
- WOS.BHCI: 2005 to 2026
- WOS.BSCI: 2005 to 2026
- WOS.ESCI: 2021 to 2026
- WOS.ISTP: 1990 to 2026
- WOS.SSCI: 1900 to 2026
- WOS.ISSHP: 1990 to 2026

If you are searching in more than the Core Collection, you may need to look for both your Core Collection entitlements AND the All Databases entitlements.

A longer way to do this is if you go to the Advanced Search page. Look at the box that says "Search in:" and "Collections:" Most likely, it will be at your institution's default search. Click on the caret next to each, and you will be able to see the complete list and full names of the multiple databases you searched. Again, if All Databases is the default search, you will also need to look at the Core Collection databases by selecting Core Collection from the Search in: area.

Thank you for your comment, we searched only in the Core Collection. We indicated this in our Methods section - search strategy.

37. **In the manuscript**, it says that you searched on Dec. 6, 2024, but in the supplementary files, it has different dates for the searches. Was the final search run on Dec. 6? If so, I would suggest updating the supplementary files.

December 6th, 2024, was indeed the latest search. No Supplementary files contain the dates of searches. The inclusion and exclusion files were downloaded from Covidence and do not reflect the dates of searches in databases.

38. Line 109, "this issue": Is "this issue" the methodological and reporting quality of SR? Or the lack of protocols and compromised reporting quality of SRP? I wasn't quite sure.

Thank you for your comment. We have revised the sentence to improve clarity and readability. The updated version now reads: *Because the quality of SRPs in environmental and occupational toxicology remains poorly characterized, we assessed their reporting quality following our previously published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025).*

39. This is for my own knowledge, but for Q6, data management, was the software/platform you were looking for regarding the search how it was deduplicated, primarily? I wasn't entirely sure.

Thank you for your comment. According to our Reporting Assessment Form available in Supplementary Material, this item refers to all softwares used during the systematic review process, including those employed for literature searching, study selection, and data extraction or critical appraisal.

40. Line 281, “Pesticides were a common focus”: It seems like it wasn’t common, comparatively? Perhaps just “focus” instead of “common focus”?
Thank you for your comment. We deleted “common focus”.
41. Line 294: Please cite ROSES and COSTER; some readers may not be familiar with them or what they are. You may wish to spell them out in an abbreviations section, though this is not necessary.
Thank you for your comment. We added their full names.
42. Table 3: Academia is missing a % after 76; chemicals is capitalized in Industrial chemicals
Thank you for your comment. We corrected it accordingly.
43. Line 354: Respiratory and nervous systems?
Thank you for your comment. We added word systems.
44. **Line 426-33:** You may want to cite something that discusses the differentiation between reporting and methodological quality. (And note perhaps, that, conversely, of course, if something is poorly reported, it is possible that it was of high methodological quality.)
Thank you for your comment. Please see answer on comment 10.
45. Line 442: Instead of “improvement in data...”, I would suggest, “improvement in reporting data...”
Thank you for your comment. We corrected it accordingly.
46. I appreciate all efforts to improve the reporting quality of systematic reviews (and their protocols), and I thank the authors for their efforts in highlighting this issue and the importance of clear and robustly reported protocols. I am happy to see this work published as a registered report, as often meta-research does not adhere to the standards which it advocates—this paper 100% does. I especially appreciated the detailed information on changes to the protocol, the data and code availability, and of course, the high quality of the reporting. I would like to see more detail on the differences between full published protocols and preregistered protocols, as well as a few other points listed above.

Thank you for your supportive and constructive comment. In Discussion we added that future studies will focus on comparative assessments of peer-reviewed and registered publications. We do not think expanding discussion in the direction of excluded population will add significant value to our study, at this stage.

Reviewer 2

47. In the introduction, the timeliness of the background information should be reassessed. As an example, line 95 cites that registration of SRP are recognized as an important step in the SR process yet this step is frequently omitted, with citation to a 2009 article. Fifteen years in the field of systematic review seems sufficiently long for me to question if this finding is still valid currently (ie, is protocol registration still frequently omitted?).

Thank you for your comment. We restructured our introduction, so it reflects more recent practices in the field.

7. Comments on summary sections

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

No reviewer comments.

8. Minor issues

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 2

In section 2.3 – are abbreviations (SHE, MPA, etc) referring to individual authors? I'm not sure this level of attribution is needed/best practice. Again, line 200-201 and 235, not sure this level of attribution is needed.

Thank you for your comment. We wanted to be transparent which reviewer was involved in which step of the process.

The structure of this evaluation report is based on the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).